

MEASURING TRAINING EFFECTIVENESS IN ACADEMIC CONTEXT: A STUDY OF FACULTY DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES

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ABSTRACT

Training is one of the most pervasive methods for enhancing the productivity of individuals and communicating organizational goals to new personnel. In the recent years, to deal with ever increasing competition and for the organizational success, training and development is seen as an important function. For this purpose organizations are investing huge budgets on training. Now it becomes a major task to create and utilize human capital. In this context, the present article aims to evaluate the effectiveness of employee training programmes in a university in Andhra Pradesh. This paper, by using Kirkpatrick's four levels model of evaluation, studies (i) the reactions of the faculty to the training program, (ii) the level of faculty learning, and (iii) the faculty's transfer of training. For this purpose, 44 respondents who attended for the FDP at a deemed university was selected by using stratified random sampling method. A feedback form designed using on Likert's Five Point scale was used as instrument to collect the data about participant reactions. An objective type test having 30 multiple choice questions covering specific subject areas was used to gauge the learning due to the Faculty Development Program (FDP). The same questionnaire was served before training and after the training to understand the level of training. To gauge the transfer of training, face to face interviews were conducted three months after the training. The results revealed that the reactions of the respondents showed overall satisfaction about the program, learning and transfer of training were also having considerable positive results.

Key Words: Training Effectiveness; Kirkpatrick's Model; FDPs; Impact of Training

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INTRODUCTION

Training is one of the most pervasive methods for enhancing the productivity of individuals and communicating organizational goals to new personnel (W.Arthur et.al, 2003). The importance of training and development need not be over emphasized. Employee training and development is an attempt to improve current or future performance of an employee to perform through learning, usually by changing the employee's attitudes or increasing his or her skills and knowledge (Wexley K N., 1984). Not only that, training is the continuous, systematic development among all levels of employees of that knowledge and those skills and attitudes which contribute to their welfare and that of the company (Mc Codd, Efferson).

Training has become a regular feature of not only industrial and corporates but also of government and non-governmental organizations. Training has successfully been used to reduce errors in such high-risk settings as emergency rooms, aviation, and the military. However, training is also important in more conventional organizations. These organizations understand that training helps them to remain competitive by continually educating their workforce. They understand that investing in their employees yields greater results (Equadro Salas, 2012). Every year thousands of crores of rupees are being spent on training by organizations. Resources, both physical as well as intellectual are being invested. The government of India has initiated a massive training programme through Sarva Siksha Abhiyaan for the teachers working in government schools to improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching at the primary level. The Indian corporate training market reached nearly \$3 billion in 2010. There is high demand for sales training, followed by soft skills such as communication and managerial effectiveness. Leadership, sales and teamwork are at the forefront of the development of Indian industry (Lin, 2009). The training market has seen tremendous growth globally as well as in India in the after years. The global market for training expenditures in 2013 was about \$306.9B, an increase from \$291.7B in 2012. Of this global market, India occupies near to \$21.5billion market share.

Effectiveness of training becomes important in view of the time and resources committed to the training and development activity. In the academic scenario, Faculty Development Programmes (FDPs) are an important mode of training the teachers. FDPs provide the orientation on appropriately delivering the subject content and also equip faculty with better understanding of the teaching practices. The present study examines the effectiveness of training and development programme rolled out as FDP in a private deemed university in Andhra Pradesh.

MEASURING TRAINING EFFECTIVENESS – KIRKPATRICK'S FRAME- WORK:

For the purpose of measuring training effectiveness, different frameworks are advocated by different researchers. Donald L Kirkpatrick, Professor Emeritus, University Of Wisconsin, first published his ideas about evaluating training programs in

1959, in a series of articles in the Journal of American Society of Training Directors. He refined his ideas in his 1994 book 'Evaluating Training Programs'. There after this model gained wider acceptance. Kirkpatrick's four-level model is now considered an industry standard across the HR and training communities. This model is the most widely used and best-known framework for evaluation (Bramley & Kitson, 1994; Kaufman & Keller, 1994; Kirkpatrick, 1994; J.J. Phillips, 1997a). The four levels of Kirkpatrick's evaluation model consist of level-1: reaction, level-2: learning, level-3: Behavior and level-4: results.

The original Kirkpatrick's model was expanded by J.J. Phillips to include Return on investment (ROI) as fifth level of evaluation. Return on investment is calculated in order to show value, in financial terms, of a training investment (J.J. Phillips, 1991). The expanded framework of Phillips comprises Level 1: reaction and planned action; Level 2: learning; Level 3: job application; Level 4: business results; and Level 5: return on investment.

A detailed description of the Kirkpatrick's model is presented below. The model is chosen as it is conceptually appropriate for the present study.

Among the four levels of Kirkpatrick's model, reaction criteria focuses on trainees' effectiveness and attitudinal response to the training programme, learning criteria looks at the learning outcomes, behavioural criteria examines improvement of job related behaviour, whereas result criteria measures the utility of the programme to the organization.

Level-1: Reaction: Evaluation of reactions is based on how the trainees felt during their learning experience. It is an attempt to capture their personal reaction to the training performance in terms of its content, delivery methods and delivery mode.

Level-2: Learning: It is an attempt to measure the learning outcomes, but not a measure of job performance. Though difficult to quantify exactly, the evaluation aims at exploring whether the trainees learnt what they are supposed to learn. It can be understood by knowing whether trainees learnt what was intended to be taught, the trainee experience, and the extent of advancement or change in the trainees after the training, in the direction or area that was intended.

Level-3: Behaviour: These criterion are measures of actual on the job performance. Behaviour evaluation is an attempt to examine the extent to which the trainees applied their newly acquired knowledge and skills on the job and improved their work related behaviour. This could be witnessed immediately or several months after the training. The idea is to examine whether the trainee is in a position to sustain as well as transfer the newly acquired knowledge and skills.

Level-4: Results: This evaluation is an attempt to examine the tangible benefits to the organizations resulting from undertaking training programmes. The Result criterion focuses on macro criteria such as productivity, profitability etc., and are frequently operationalized by using utility analysis estimates.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mehta (1970) points out that the training effectiveness depends on the kind of atmosphere and culture prevalent in the organization.

Fast (1994) worked on evaluation mechanisms for quantitative measurement the programme effectiveness.

Eltington(1984) proposed that participants reactions might be obtained by various groups in actions, devices including self appraisal, circular whip, fish bowl movement , individual critique and group critique. Similarly to judge the learning of participants, methods such as observations, attitude survey and review of proposed action plans are suggested.

Sikka(1985) suggested two models to evaluate training effectiveness which are useful in generating comparative data to judge if training has really made an impression.

Swanson and Sleezer (1987) developed and pilot tested a practical training effectiveness evaluation (TEE) system that could be applied to any training programme in industry.

Perdue, Ninemeier, and Woods (2002) assessed perceived relative effectiveness of alternative training methods (in relation to specific objectives) among managers of private clubs. The results indicated that one-to-one training is considered the most useful over all methods and the preferred method for all objectives except interpersonal skill development.

Alvarez et al., (2004) in his research on training effectiveness and evaluation found that evaluation measures that as found to be related to post-training attitudes are cognitive learning, training performance, and transfer of performance.

Khattak et al., (2011) carried a study to measure the input of the in-service teacher training programmes suggested that to increase the impact of training on teacher performance, instructors based on merit and need, practical and trainee-oriented approach of trainer and training, tailoring the content and training environment and allowing focused training by grouping trainees according to their job position or level.

Mohammad Khani and Ashrafi (2013) conducted a study by using Kirkpatrick's mode to evaluate the effectiveness of tour guides training programme in Tehran. They concluded that the tour guides training programme in Tehran were effective.

Siengthai et al., (2014) conducted a study on in-service training programmes conducted in public sector organizations in Thailand. The training effectiveness is dependent on several factors such as the input into the training programmes, namely, participant's and instructors' skills, knowledge and abilities, the training process itself which depends on the contents and methods used in the programmes.

METHODOLOGY

The present paper is an attempt to study the effectiveness of the Faculty Development Programme (FDP) conducted at a private deemed university in Andhra

Pradesh. Translating the understanding from the Kirkpatrick's evaluation model, this paper particularly focuses on knowing about:

- (i) the reactions of the faculty to the training program;
- (ii) the level of faculty's learning; and
- (iii) the faculty's transfer of training

The study is based on the FDP programme conducted during the month of **September, 2014** and the post training data was collected during **December, 2014** leaving a three month window period to let the transfer of training progress. A sample of 44 respondents who attended the FDP in September 2014 was selected as respondents. The FDP was arranged as a part of improving teaching skills of newly joined and existing faculty, by providing them with the methods of teaching in general and improving the subject specific background knowledge. A feedback form was designed using 5-point Likert scale to capture the faculty reactions to training. The Feedback Form covered the feelings of faculty on the course structure, training materials, facilities, training setting and resource persons. An objective type test having 30 multiple choice questions covering specific subject areas was used to gauge the learning due to the FDP. The same questionnaire was served before the training and 10 days after training to understand level of learning. To gauge the transfer of training, face to face interviews were conducted three months after the training. All the respondents were interviewed and their opinions were recorded to understand the extent of applying what they learnt during FDP.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION:

Demographic Distribution of Respondents:

Table:1 Demographic distribution of respondents:

S.No.	Factor	Frequency	Percentage	
1	Gender	Male	28	64
		Female	16	36
2	Experience	Less than 5 years	19	43
		5-9 years	15	34
		More than 10 years	10	23
3	Education Levels	Post-graduate	30	68
		M.Phil	8	18
		Ph.D	6	14
4	Faculty / Subject	Engineering	24	55
		Sciences & Humanities	12	27
		Management	8	18

Source: Primary data

The findings from table no. 5.1 showed that the distribution was higher for males with total of 28 male representations (64%). On the other hand there were 16

female respondents (36%). When the level of experience is considered 34% of total participants fall in between 5 to 9 years of experience and rests of the 23% are falling more than ten years of experience. The data also indicates that 68% of the participants are post-graduates, 18% are having M.phil qualification and rest of the 14% are with Ph.D. qualification. As far as the participants' teaching branches of specialization are concerned 55% belonging to engineering stream while 27 % are from faculty of science and humanities and rest of the 18% represented management stream.

Level 1: Reactions

Table : 2 Reactions of Respondents about the FDP:

S.No.	Factor		Rating	Mean Values
1	Programme	Objectives were clearly communicated	4.52	4.08
		Objectives were met	3.91	
		Duration was sufficient	3.45	
		Contents were suitable to context	4.45	
2	Resources	Learning material was supportive	3.45	4.02
		Learning methods were relevant	3.68	
		Training room and facilities were appropriate	4.36	
		Logistics and food arrangements were satisfactory	4.56	
3	Resource Persons	Were Knowledgeable	3.96	4.28
		Were engaging and encouraging learning	4.65	
		Delivered content accordingly	4.25	
4	Overall FDP	The programme gave overall satisfaction	4.35	4.35

Source: Primary data

The above table represents the reactions of the participants on FDP they attended in 2014. Among the factors considered about the participant reactions, the findings showed that the mean scores on a 5 point Likert scale to the overall assessment criteria was 4.35 followed by 4.08 for the program, 4.02 for the resources and 4.28 for the resource persons. The participants of FDP programs were highly satisfied with the way the objectives were clearly communicated and met with sufficient duration of the time in highly appropriate context. The mean values of the total programs indicate that the participants are highly satisfied.

As far as the resources are concerned, the participant's expressed their satisfaction regarding the supportive learning materials, relevance of learning methods, availability of appropriate training facilities and logistics and food arrangements. The

respondents are highly satisfied with the resource persons. The participant's expressed that the resource persons arranged for FDP, as they were very knowledgeable, were engaging and encouraging, learning and delivered good content accordingly. The mean value of 4.28 indicates their level of satisfaction.

Level 2: Learning

Table : 3 Comparison of Pre training and Post training Test results:

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	Score in Pre Test before FDP	Score in Post Test after FDP
Mean	16.52273	24.56818182
Variance	8.999471	5.134778013
Observations	44	44
Pearson Correlation	0.687402	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	43	
t Stat	-24.3878	
P(T<=t) one-tail	4.13E-27	
t Critical one-tail	1.681071	
P(T<=t) two-tail	8.25E-27	
t Critical two-tail	2.016692	

Source: Primary data

H_0 : There is no significant effect of training on participant learning

H_1 : There is a significant effect of training on participant learning

Calculated value of $|t|$ greater than the tabulated value of 't' at 5 percent level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3 depicts the comparison of the test scores of participants before and after training to understand the impact of training on learning.

It can be clearly understood that there is significant effect of training on participant learning. The scores obtained in the pre-test conducted before training have improved significantly in the post-test conducted after training, indicating good learning from the training.

Level 3: Behavior (Transfer of training)

Table : 4 Respondents views on their ability to apply training inputs

S.No.	Factor	Frequency	Percentage	
1	Behaviour / Ability to Transfer of Learning	Able to apply the learning of FDP totally	18	41
		Able to apply the learning of FDP Partially	13	30
		Able to apply the learning of FDP to limited extent	11	25
		Not Able to apply the learning of FDP	2	5

Source: Primary data - Compiled based on interview of respondents

Three months after the FDP, the researcher conducted a one to one (face to face) interview with the participants. The findings showed that the most of participants who gained knowledge skills and attitude during training are able to apply them in their departments or workplace. Among the participants, 41% are able to apply the learning of FDP totally, 30% are able to apply the learning of FDP partially and 25 % are able to apply the learning of FDP to limited extent. Few participants i.e. at 5% were only not able to apply the learning of FDP. Over all transfer of knowledge to their respective work places is very high and highly satisfactory.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper attempted to evaluate the effectiveness of training programmes in education sector by using the Kirkpatrick's four levels of evaluation model. The present study observed that most of the respondents were satisfied with the programme, resources and resource persons of the training programme. The participants were satisfied and convinced with learning activities provided to them and interest created to learn. The study also revealed that the respondents have improved their knowledge and were able to apply the learning at their work place. It is suggested to the organization that they should continue training programs in future by taking the feedback from the current programmes.

The present study is limited to understand the training effectiveness based on one FDP and the corresponding follow-up activities only. However, the validity and reliability of the conclusions can be improved by making a review of various FDPs offered over a period of time. The study also does not cover the fourth level of Kirkpatrick's evaluation model aimed at gauging the results for the organization.

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